

Supplementary material: High-Quality Human Motion Prediction Using Size Invariant Motion Space

Haichuan Zhao^a, Xudong Ru^a, Peng Du^a, Shaolong Liu^b, Na Liu^c, Xingce Wang^{a,*} and Zhongke Wu^{a,**}

^aSchool of Artificial Intelligence, Beijing Normal University

^bSchool of Arts and Communication, Beijing Normal University

^cInformation Science Academy of China Electronics Technology Group Corporation

1 Geometry Tools of Pose Space

The exponential map of \mathbb{S}^2 denotes as:

$$\exp_{s_i}(\nu) = \cos(\|\nu\|)s_i + \frac{\sin(\|\nu\|)}{\|\nu\|}\nu$$

The logarithm map of \mathbb{S}^2 is

$$\log_{s_i}(s_j) = \frac{\rho}{\sin(\rho)}(s_j - s_i \cos(\rho)),$$

and the parallel transport from s_i to s_j on \mathbb{S}^2 is denoted as:

$$pt_{s_i \rightarrow s_j}(\nu) = \nu - \frac{\langle s_j, \nu \rangle}{1 + \cos(\rho)}(s_i + s_j),$$

where $s_i, s_j \in \mathbb{S}^2$, $\nu \in T_{s_i}\mathbb{S}^2$, $\nu' \in T_{s_j}\mathbb{S}^2$, ρ is the Riemannian distance in \mathbb{S}^2 , and $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ is the Euclidean inner product.

Due to the pose space being a product manifold composed of $(K-1)\mathbb{S}^2$ manifolds, we can leverage the properties of product manifolds to define geometric tools on the pose space \mathcal{P} . The exponential map **Exp**, logarithm map **Log** and parallel transport **Pt** of \mathcal{P} are respectively denoted as:

$$\mathbf{Exp}_p(V) = (\exp_{s_1}(\nu_1), \dots, \exp_{s_{K-1}}(\nu_{K-1}))$$

$$\mathbf{Log}_p(p') = (\log_{s_1}(s'_1), \dots, \log_{s_{K-1}}(s'_{K-1}))$$

$$\mathbf{Pt}_{p \rightarrow p'}(V) = (pt_{s_1 \rightarrow s'_1}(\nu_1), \dots, pt_{s_{K-1} \rightarrow s'_{K-1}}(\nu_{K-1}))$$

where $p, p' \in \mathcal{P}$, $V \in T_p\mathcal{P}$, and $s_k, s'_k \in \mathbb{S}_k^2$.

2 Proof that TTSRVF is the Isometric Mapping between MS and TTSRVF's space

This proof is based on [2, 1].

Proof. Let

$$C_p(\xi, \zeta) = \int_0^1 \langle \nabla_s \xi^\top, \nabla_s \zeta^\top \rangle + \frac{1}{4} \langle \nabla_s \xi, \partial_s p \rangle \langle \nabla_s \zeta, \partial_s p \rangle ds \quad (1)$$

* Corresponding Author. Email: wangxingce@bnu.edu.cn.

** Corresponding Author. Email: zwu@bnu.edu.cn.

where $\xi, \zeta \in T_c\mathcal{C}$, $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ depend on the $p(s)$, $p(s)$ is the arc length parameterization of $c(t)$. As the manuscript, the TTSRVF is defined as

$$\alpha(t) = \psi(p)(t) = \frac{\dot{p}(t)_{p(t) \cap p(0)}}{\sqrt{\|\dot{p}(t)\|_2}}$$

where $\psi : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$, $\mathcal{H} = \{\alpha \in L^2(I, T_\tau\mathcal{P}) | \alpha = \psi(p)\}$. First, we need to check that its differential, $d(\psi) : T\mathcal{C} \rightarrow T\mathcal{H}$, thus $d(\psi)_p : T_p\mathcal{C} \rightarrow T_p\mathcal{H}$. For $\xi, \zeta \in T_p\mathcal{C}$, the results of differential mapping are $d(\psi)_p(\xi), d(\psi)_p(\zeta) \in T_p\mathcal{H}$. According to the results [2], the equivalent definition of ψ is $\psi(p) = e^{\frac{1}{2}\phi}\theta$, where $\phi = \ln(\|\dot{p}\|)$, $\theta = \frac{\dot{p}}{\|\dot{p}\|_2}$. Then, the differential mapping $d(\psi)_p$ acts on ξ, ζ , the results as following:

$$\begin{aligned} d(\psi)_c(\xi) &= \frac{1}{2}e^{\frac{1}{2}\phi} \langle \nabla_s \xi, \partial_s p \rangle \theta \\ &+ e^{\frac{1}{2}\phi} (\nabla_s \xi - \langle \nabla_s \xi, \partial_s p \rangle \partial_s p) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}e^{\frac{1}{2}\phi} \langle \nabla_s \xi, \partial_s p \rangle \theta + e^{\frac{1}{2}\phi} \nabla_s \xi^\top \end{aligned}$$

where $\nabla_s \xi, \nabla_s \zeta \in T_\alpha\mathcal{H}$, then $\langle \nabla_s \xi, \partial_s p \rangle$ is projection along the tangent direction of c , quantifying the change in speed resulting from the motion variation. The $\nabla_s \xi^\top$ is the orthogonal component, it measures the variations in motion direction caused by the motion changes. Computing the \mathbb{L}^2 inner product of $d(\psi)_c(\xi)$ and $d(\psi)_c(\zeta)$ yields

$$\begin{aligned} \langle d(\psi)_c(\xi), d(\psi)_c(\zeta) \rangle &= \int_0^T \frac{1}{4} e^\phi \langle \nabla_s \xi, \partial_s p \rangle \langle \nabla_s \zeta, \partial_s p \rangle \\ &+ e^\phi \langle \nabla_s \xi^\top, \nabla_s \zeta^\top \rangle dt \\ &= \int_0^1 \frac{1}{4} \langle \nabla_s \xi, \partial_s p \rangle \langle \nabla_s \zeta, \partial_s p \rangle \\ &+ \langle \nabla_s \xi^\top, \nabla_s \zeta^\top \rangle ds \end{aligned}$$

In this, the facts that $\langle \theta, \theta \rangle = 1$ since $\theta(t)$ is an element of the unit sphere and $\langle \theta, \nabla_s \zeta^\top \rangle = 0$ since $\nabla_s \zeta^\top$ is the tangent vector to the unit sphere at $\theta(t)$ and $e^\phi dt = ds$ are used. Therefore, SP-TSRVF is the isometric mapping between (\mathcal{C}, G) and $(\mathcal{H}, \mathbb{L}^2)$. And geodesics with respect to the metric (1) correspond to straight lines under the TTSRVF. \square

Remark. It should be clarified that the symbol θ used here has a different meaning from the manuscript.

3 Visualization of prediction results

We have visualized some of the results, as shown in Figures 1, 2, and 3.

References

- [1] M. Bauer, M. Bruveris, and P. W. Michor. *Why Use Sobolev Metrics on the Space of Curves*, pages 233–255. Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2016. ISBN 978-3-319-22957-7. doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-22957-7_11.
- [2] A. Srivastava, E. Klassen, S. H. Joshi, and I. H. Jermyn. Shape analysis of elastic curves in euclidean spaces. *IEEE Trans. Pattern. Anal. and Mach. Intell.*, 33(7):1415–1428, 2010. doi: 10.1109/TPAMI.2010.184.

Figure 1. Visualization of prediction results of sitting on Human 3.6M datasets.

Figure 2. Visualization of prediction results of walking on Human 3.6M datasets.

Figure 3. Visualization of prediction results of walkingdog on Human 3.6M datasets.